

DNS of lean hydrogen-air flames with different chemistry and transport modelling approaches

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Outline

- Introduction
- Computational setup
- 1D results
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- Future work
- Funding sources & acknowledgments

Introduction

- Hydrogen's high mass diffusivity gives rise to diffusive-thermal **instabilities**: cellular flame fronts
- Instabilities do **increase the overall flame propagation rate** by an order of magnitude w.r.t. the planar case (canonical solution)
- **Cellular structures persist** even in confined geometries with heat losses, thus raising **safety concerns**
- Previous numerical simulations (Frouzakis et al. 2015, Berger et al. 2019, Dejoan et al. 2024) have studied this problem
 - **Single-step** reaction mechanism
 - **Simplified** transport modelling
 - **Low-order** numerical schemes

$\phi=0.8$, $s_L=9.7\text{cm/s}$, $S_c=48\text{cm/s}$, FoV: 59.7cm x 39.4cm x 1.27cm.
 S. Shen, X. Ma, J. Wongwiwat, J. Gross, P.D. Ronney, 10th U.S.
 National Combustion Meeting, Combustion Institute, 2017, April
 23-26, College Park, Maryland

Introduction

- This work is a **collaboration** between UPC, BSC, and CIEMAT as a result of the **HPCCOMB2023**
- Generation of a high-fidelity and accurate **DNS dataset for the scientific community**
- Systematic **comparative study**
 - Combustion regime (above ultra-lean) regime: $\phi=0.27, 0.30, 0.40,$ and 0.50
 - Transport modelling: constant Lewis vs. full description
 - Kinetic effects: one-step vs. detailed
- How does the **physical modelling** influence the **flame behaviour**?
- What are the **limits of the one-step reduced mechanism** (D. Fernández-Galisteo et al. 2009)?

$\phi=0.8, s_L=9.7\text{cm/s}, S_c=48\text{cm/s}, \text{FoV}: 59.7\text{cm} \times 39.4\text{cm} \times 1.27\text{cm}.$
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Computational setup: CREAMS

- Numerical simulations are conducted with the CFD software **CREAMS**
- It solves the full Navier-Stokes equations for compressible, reactive, and multi-species flows
- **Fortran 90** massively parallel code developed between 2010-2013
 - P.J. Martinez-Ferrer, PhD thesis
 - Main CFD framework used in 5 additional PhD thesis
- Extensively run on **several European supercomputers**
 - IBM BlueGene/P and /Q (France)
 - ARCHER Cray XC30 and Hartree (UK)
 - MareNostrum 4 and 5 (Spain)

Buttay et al. (2014)

Miller et al. (1998)

Martinez-Ferrer et al. (2016)

Techer et al. (2016)

Boukharfane et al. (2019)

Computational setup: Navier-Stokes equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_j}{\partial x_j} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial \rho u_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_i u_j}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} &= \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j}, \quad i = 1, \dots, 3, \\ \frac{\partial \rho e_t}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\rho e_t + p) u_j}{\partial x_j} &= \frac{\partial u_i \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial q_j}{\partial x_j}, \\ \frac{\partial \rho Y_\alpha}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho Y_\alpha u_j}{\partial x_j} &= -\frac{\partial \rho Y_\alpha V_{\alpha j}}{\partial x_j} + \text{X}, \quad \alpha = 1, \dots, N, \\ \frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} &= L_i(Q(t)) = -\frac{\partial F_j}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial G_j}{\partial x_j}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} h_\alpha(T) &= \Delta h_{f\alpha}^0 + \int_{T_0}^T c_{p\alpha}(T^*) dT^* \\ &= \frac{R}{W_\alpha} \left(a_{6\alpha} + a_{1\alpha}T + a_{2\alpha} \frac{T^2}{2} + a_{3\alpha} \frac{T^3}{3} + a_{4\alpha} \frac{T^4}{4} + a_{5\alpha} \frac{T^5}{5} \right), \\ c_{p\alpha}(T) &= \frac{R}{W_\alpha} \left(a_{1\alpha} + a_{2\alpha}T + a_{3\alpha}T^2 + a_{4\alpha}T^3 + a_{5\alpha}T^4 \right), \\ h &= \sum_{\alpha=1}^N Y_\alpha h_\alpha, \quad c_p = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N Y_\alpha c_{p\alpha}, \quad W = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N X_\alpha W_\alpha = \left(\sum_{\alpha=1}^N \frac{Y_\alpha}{W_\alpha} \right)^{-1}, \\ p &= \frac{\rho RT}{W}, \quad c_v = c_p - \frac{R}{W}, \quad e_t = e + \frac{u_i u_i}{2}, \quad e = h - \frac{p}{\rho}. \end{aligned}$$

- Full **Navier-Stokes** equations for compressible, **inert**, and multi-species flows

- Species enthalpies and specific heat capacities determined from **JANAF** thermochemical tables
- Equation of state of an **ideal mixture of gases** to close the system of equations

Computational setup: Transport terms

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_{ij} &= 2\mu \left(S_{ij} - \frac{S_{kk}}{3} \delta_{ij} \right), \quad S_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right), \\ \rho Y_\alpha V_{\alpha j} &= -\rho D_{m\alpha} \frac{W_\alpha}{W} \frac{\partial X_\alpha}{\partial x_j} + \rho Y_\alpha V_c \\ &= -\rho D_{m\alpha} \frac{W_\alpha}{W} \frac{\partial X_\alpha}{\partial x_j} + \rho Y_\alpha \sum_{\beta=1}^N D_{m\beta} \frac{W_\beta}{W} \frac{\partial X_\beta}{\partial x_j}, \\ q_j &= -\lambda \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} + \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \rho Y_\alpha V_{\alpha j} h_\alpha, \\ D_{m\alpha} &= \frac{\lambda}{\rho c_p \text{Le}_\alpha}.\end{aligned}$$

Simplified transport

- **Viscosity** and **thermal conductivity** computed with the **CHEMKIN** library (Kee et al., 1996)
- **Average** mass species diffusion $D_{m\alpha}$ assumes **constant Lewis**

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_{ij} &= \kappa S_{kk} \delta_{ij} + 2\mu \left(S_{ij} - \frac{S_{kk}}{3} \delta_{ij} \right), \quad S_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right), \\ \rho Y_\alpha V_{\alpha j} &= -\sum_{\beta=1}^N \rho \tilde{D}_{\alpha\beta} d_{\beta j} - \rho Y_\alpha \theta_\alpha \frac{\partial \ln T}{\partial x_j} \\ &= -\sum_{\beta=1}^N \rho \tilde{D}_{\alpha\beta} \left(d_{\beta j} + \frac{X_\beta \tilde{\chi}_\beta}{T} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right), \\ d_{\beta j} &= \frac{\partial X_\beta}{\partial x_j} + \frac{X_\beta - Y_\beta}{p} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_j}, \\ q_j &= -\lambda' \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} + \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \rho Y_\alpha V_{\alpha j} h_\alpha - p \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \theta_\alpha d_{\alpha j} \\ &= -\lambda \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} + \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \rho Y_\alpha V_{\alpha j} \left(h_\alpha + \frac{RT \tilde{\chi}_\alpha}{W_\alpha} \right),\end{aligned}$$

Detailed transport

- **Volume** viscosity κ
- **Differential** diffusion matrix $D_{\alpha\beta}$
- **Thermodiffusion** and **barodiffusion**
- Terms computed with the **EGLIB** library (Ern & Giovangigli, 1995)

Computational setup: Reaction terms

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{RT}{c_v} \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \frac{\dot{\omega}_{\alpha}}{W_{\alpha}} - \frac{\sum_{\alpha=1}^N h_{\alpha} \dot{\omega}_{\alpha}}{c_v},$$

$$\frac{dY_{\alpha}}{dt} = \dot{\omega}_{\alpha}, \quad \alpha = 1, \dots, N,$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = L_r(Q(t)) = S.$$

- **PSR** at constant volume at every point
- No need for the **VODE** library (Brown et al., 1989) for such small time steps!

$$\nu'_c C + \nu'_o O \rightarrow \nu''_p P,$$

$$\sum_{\alpha=1}^N \nu'_{\alpha,i} M_{\alpha} \rightleftharpoons \sum_{\alpha=1}^N \nu''_{\alpha,i} M_{\alpha}, \quad i = 1, \dots, R,$$

$$q_i = k_{f,i} \prod_{\alpha=1}^N [X_{\alpha}]^{\nu'_{\alpha,i}} - k_{r,i} \prod_{\alpha=1}^N [X_{\alpha}]^{\nu''_{\alpha,i}},$$

$$k_{f,i} = A_i T^{\beta_i} \exp\left(\frac{-E_{A_i}}{RT}\right),$$

$$\dot{\omega}_{\alpha} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_r} \dot{\omega}_{\alpha,i} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_r} (\nu''_{\alpha,i} - \nu'_{\alpha,i}) q_i.$$

- Species productions computed with the **CHEMKIN** library
- **Simplified kinetics: One-step reduced kinetics** (D. Fernández-Galisteo et al., 2009)
- **Detailed kinetics: Full San Diego mechanism** (9 species & 23 reactions)

Computational setup: Temporal & spatial discretisation

$$Q^{n+1} = [L_r(\Delta t/2)L_i(\Delta t)L_r(\Delta t/2)] Q^n.$$

$$Q^{(1)} = Q^n + \Delta t L_i(Q^n),$$

$$Q^{(2)} = \frac{1}{4} [3Q^n + Q^{(1)} + \Delta t L_i(Q^{(1)})],$$

$$Q^{n+1} = \frac{1}{3} [Q^n + 2Q^{(2)} + 2\Delta t L_i(Q^{(2)})].$$

- 2nd-order **Strang splitting** (Strang, 1968) couples the inert and reactive systems
- 3rd-order **Runge-Kutta** TVD for the inert system: convective (F) and viscous (G) fluxes
- 1st-order update for the reactive system

Convective fluxes

- Local Lax Friedrich (LLF) advective flux reconstruction
- 8th-order **skew-symmetric** interpolation scheme with no numerical viscosity (Pirozzoli, 2010)
- 10th-order **explicit dissipative filter** (Kennedy & Carpenter, 1994)
- **WENO7** interpolation at non-reflecting boundaries

Diffusive fluxes

- 8th-order **centred** scheme
- Second derivative obtained from applying the first derivative twice

Computational setup: Conditions

Boundary conditions

- NSCBC boundary conditions (Cousement et al., 2012) at the inlet and outlet boundaries helped with sponges to better absorb perturbations
- Periodicity imposed at the top and bottom boundaries for 2D problems

Initial conditions

- 1D: laminar premixed flame initialised with erf function
- 2D: starts from the converged flame (1D) with a perturbation along the flame

Computational setup: Cases

- Four regimes: $\phi=0.5, 0.4, 0.3,$ and 0.27
 - Detailed mech., detailed transport: 1000 kh, 6272 CPUs, 550
 - Detailed mech., constant Lewis: 400 kh, 3136 CPUs, 550 GB
 - One-step, detailed transport: 400 kh, 3136 CPUs, 350 GB
 - One-step, constant Lewis: 200 kh, 3136 CPUs, 350 GB
- RES computational project IM-2025-2-0016
 - 6.6 Mh
 - MN5-GPP: 2x Intel Xeon Platinum 8480+ 56c 2GHz
- Much of this work is still in progress

1D results

$\phi=0.27$, one-step mech., constant Lewis

1D results

- Richest mixture ($\phi=0.5$) yields largest discrepancies between cases
- Constant Lewis assumption heavily constraints the shape of the hydrogen distribution
- The most detailed physical description always differentiates from the rest of the cases, regardless of the equivalence ratio

1D results

- Once more, the largest discrepancies between cases correspond to $\phi=0.5$
- Detailed kinetics release heat over the entire flame front
- Detailed transport helps widening the release of heat for $\phi=0.4$ and $\phi=0.5$

1D results

ϕ	Transport	Chemistry	δL (m)	SL (m/s)	Δx (m)	L (m)
0.5	Le cst.	one-step	2.00E-04	6.98E-01	2.50E-05	1.20E-01
0.5	detailed	one-step	1.97E-04	7.07E-01	2.50E-05	1.20E-01
0.5	Le cst.	detailed	3.53E-04	4.80E-01	2.50E-05	1.20E-01
0.5	detailed	detailed	4.00E-04	5.45E-01	2.50E-05	1.20E-01
0.4	Le cst.	one-step	3.54E-04	3.10E-01	4.00E-05	1.80E-01
0.4	detailed	one-step	3.54E-04	3.14E-01	4.00E-05	1.80E-01
0.4	Le cst.	detailed	5.26E-04	2.37E-01	4.00E-05	1.80E-01
0.4	detailed	detailed	5.94E-04	2.40E-01	4.00E-05	1.80E-01
0.3	Le cst.	one-step	1.83E-03	4.60E-02	1.50E-04	5.50E-01
0.3	detailed	one-step	1.85E-03	4.50E-02	1.50E-04	5.50E-01
0.3	Le cst.	detailed	1.79E-03	5.22E-02	1.50E-04	5.50E-01
0.3	detailed	detailed	2.03E-03	4.74E-02	1.50E-04	5.50E-01
0.27	Le cst.	one-step	4.50E-03	1.68E-02	2.00E-04	1.40E+00
0.27	detailed	one-step	4.77E-03	1.60E-02	2.00E-04	1.40E+00
0.27	Le cst.	detailed	4.61E-03	1.70E-02	2.00E-04	1.40E+00
0.27	detailed	detailed	5.13E-03	1.50E-02	2.00E-04	1.40E+00

2D results

- $\phi=0.4$
- One-step reduced chemistry
- Top: constant Lewis
- Bottom: detailed transport
- With constant Lewis, the flame front advances further to the inlet

2D results

- $\phi=0.4$
- Detailed chemistry
- Top: constant Lewis
- Bottom: detailed transport
- Cell structures continue to propagate parallel to the inlet flow
- Further computational time required required to get fully statistically convergence and compare with Berger

2D results

- Only $\phi=0.4$ results obtained so far
- Detailed kinetics cases have not reached convergence yet (0.10 s)
- One-step simulations do accelerate before than san Diego ones
- Simple kinetics with constant Lewis yields faster propagation velocities
 - Berger et al. (2019) reported $S_c/S_L \approx 4.1$
 - Dejoan et al. (2024) reported $S_c/S_L \approx 4.4$

Future work

- Achieve steadiness with $\phi=0.4$ and detailed kinetics
- Complete the cases with $\phi=0.5$ (and begin lower equivalence ratios)
- Carry on more thorough post-treatment analysis of the data
- Extend this work to 3D simulations

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